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For Novice zeal to teach, can Experience be an obstruction?

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Abstract

After a number of rejections from different academic institutions, the author rationalized to write this study paper inquiring to all the concerned persons; is experience the only quality to be a good teacher? A novice can never be a good teacher? To start a teaching career, how a novice can have experience although s/he strongly possesses adequate content knowledge (CK) and effective teaching performance level (TP). These days it's vivid that CK has illogically been ignored in context of Nepal. Furthermore no one counts teaching performance in the classroom. With this mind set, the paper was written with the purpose of exploring of the reasons why is teaching experience regularly being asked by the school/college's owner in general and being specific to English Teacher. This issue has been critically analyzed and summed up that the content knowledge and teacher performance has a crucial role in professional development of a teacher.

**Study
Context**

**The
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Keywords: Content Knowledge (CK), Teaching Experience (TE), Teaching Performance, for experience and getting rejected from the job thought of a new way to deal the situation, and the journey of this research commenced from the day when he was asked for the teaching experience in his first interview for the teacher. In the interview, he was asked the question "Do you have teaching experience?" The reply was 'NO, sir'. That was the reason the result did not favour him, and he was simply rejected from the job without any consideration. This is the fate of many enthusiastic fresh interviewees in every interview. The trend of seeking experience is a burning issue in each interview which pressurizes fresher and keeps them away from interviews. Moreover, the fresh candidates get frustrated as well.

Previously set scoring provision for teaching experience lacks them behind in total score. Such energetic and calibre candidates, being frustrated by such provision, are forced to leave the field with heavy heart. The researcher was not the exception! His ultimate dream to become a teacher and occupy some professional space in the realm of teaching was devastated by the bombarding of such questions in each interview.

So far the context is concerned; it was researched when he was an M. Ed. Scholar at Tribhuvan University, School of Education with remarkable scores. He was highly inspired by the question, 'Do you have teaching experience?' and led to research on its significance in terms of administrative concern and novice zeal. The ignorance of the candidates' knowledge on the field and overemphasis on experience seemed really stressful ever in his professional career.

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This article aims to knock the teacher recruitment departments and urge them to give importance to the depth of subject matter a novice can hold. The trend of keeping teaching experience on the canopy of criteria for teachers' selection needs to be revised as it insists on experience and only experience and keeps the knowledge aside. To fulfill the pre-designed provision a parroted question is fired: Do you have teaching experience? And there follows a SORRY adding: we need an experienced teacher. The ignorance of one's knowledge leads competitive would be teachers away making space for those with experience. Personally, I am not against any experienced teachers and I just want to add the point that experience and content knowledge should go hand in hand. More specifically, the article has depicted the reasons why the candidates' content knowledge should be respected.

Content, Performance and Experience

Trio components of teaching success are: content, performance, and experience. Generally, content knowledge refers to the knowledge of the subject matter which enables us: what to teach, why to teach and how much to teach. Richards (1997) says "content knowledge is defined as the core set of theory, concept, and practice regarding second language learning and teaching which provides a kind of extra confidence for teaching" (p.1). It means a deep understanding of the subject that we teach is more important, and that should be covered in teaching. From this we can say that the content knowledge is a teacher's underlying knowledge to deliver the content. Moreover, the content knowledge also includes the knowledge of different methods and techniques of teaching. No doubt, the fresh candidates carry ideas of new techniques too.

On the other hand, experience is the practical knowledge that a person gains from his/her job. Here, we are talking about teaching, and teaching experience is gained when one enters the teaching field. Kini and Polodsky (2016) define that the *extra knowledge* of a teacher achieved from teaching is taken as teaching experience. It has high significance for a teacher in terms of managing classes in general and teaching confidently in particular. It is subject to our context too. The advertisement demands certain years experience in teaching which bars many candidates without checking their knowledge and command.

Performance is the action or process of performing certain task. A teacher's ability to handle the class, deliver the content with confidence, dedication towards the job and more importantly sound knowledge of subject matter play important role in successful teaching. In addition to these, ability to accept the students and handle them and zeal to make them learn also are remarkable milestones. Many years teaching experience may not necessarily add these qualities. Kini and Polodsky (2016) clearly stated that some time a novice teacher can also teach confidently with good command. This statement implies that the paradigm of thinking an experienced teacher only can teach does not remain constant.

Teaching is a noble job that gives dignified life to many should be chosen with profound concern. While making criteria, content knowledge and performance should be added

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considering the fact that experience is obtained only when a fresh candidate jumps into the field. For experience he/she needs a start. To conclude, a person with adequate content knowledge and performance should also be given chance to make space in teaching field.

Role of Content Knowledge and Performance in Teacher Development

Teacher development is a collaborative process which comprises reviewing, renewal and enhancing of thinking and practice. Performance is the actual practice of ideas and content. As content knowledge provides a teacher with confidence and mastery over the content to be delivered along with the techniques and strategies to be adopted, it definitely promotes performance. A teacher in the field practices his/her knowledge and gives the performance. The more he develops his content knowledge and indulges in practice the more he can develop. Definitely, only entering the classes and teaching the mere content provided by the textbook would not be sufficient. That's why in service trainings and academic qualification are also demanded during promotions. If frequent trainings, upgraded qualification, and selection of teachers with higher degrees than mentioned in the vacancy for the teachers verify that content knowledge play important role. Then why the teaching experience becomes an issue during the selection. The central idea is that content knowledge plays vital role in professional development and so does in teaching. A teacher's development directly depends on his/her knowledge on the subject. Moreover, lack of knowledge lags him/her behind no matter how long teaching history one holds. The meaningful interaction amongst teachers, administration, parents, community, and the education department itself can promote teacher development. On the other hand, demanding experience as the bottom line prevents a would- be-teacher's right to prove him/her. Ball at al. (2007) stated that the content knowledge leads a teacher to almost exclusively in general aspects of teaching: classroom management, time allocation, and planning. From this we can say that content knowledge is the subject to be addressed in the professional development. In this regard, Grossman (1990) concluded that it is inherent and unavoidable part that teachers must know psychology, subject matter for teaching to make them more accessible to students. From this I want to draw the attention of the authority that without content knowledge teaching will not be effective, for content helps teachers what and how to select, plan, deliver, and teach. The basic knowledge every teacher needs is: the content knowledge. Later he can develop other ideas and techniques implementing the theoretical knowledge he/she has gained and practices he did during his/her university degrees. Here I choose to highlight the fact that the respect to the depth of content knowledge in selection can generate more qualified teachers. Though it completely breaks the traditional hypothesis that experienced teachers only can give better performance and removes one question from the questionnaire, make some hope to the fresh candidates.

From my experience, I can say that the majority of private schools and colleges prefer teachers who have better teaching experiences in the context of Nepal. In the name of teaching experience the content knowledge and the skills have been simply ignored. However, content

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knowledge helps a novice teacher to teach his/her students a lesson correctly as well as confidently where a teacher becomes able to gain teaching experience while teaching. In this line, Ball, et al. (2007) noted that the content and the knowledge of subject matter, makes a novice teacher creative because content knowledge is the first ornament that every good teacher should have. As it plays the significant role in teacher's professional development, it should also be embraced and respected in our context. From above discussion we can draw the conclusion that content knowledge should not be ignored and one day's performance whilst selection can also be the mirror to project what sort of professional one can be in future. I strongly urge from above discussions and citations that content knowledge and performance should be tested and given importance at the time of recruiting a new teacher for any educational organization.

Why Teaching Experience

During my studies and determination to explore the reason behind advocating for the teaching experience, I traced most of the researches depicted that teachers with teaching experience perform better. Similar understanding prevails in the arena of Nepalese society and teacher recruitment is affected too with the enquiry of teaching experience. Teacher recruitment committee hopes that the experienced teachers will have command over the content; manage classes well; teach confidently; and will also have better command in language use, especially in the context of medium of teaching. We cannot completely deny the fact that the journey of teaching teaches them a lot. Their level of understanding and maturity in handling various situations like students with gifted ability or students with different abilities enhances their performance. In this regard, King (2010) believes that among many factors, teacher's teaching experience seems one of the notable factors in the field of teaching that has crucial role in making a teaching bold and focused in his/her teaching. It means experience makes a teacher confident enough to teach. On the other hand, there are some other studies that have still been showing that only teaching experiences are not the factor that develops a novice into a teacher who is better professionally.

The educational institutes in Nepal poise a strong mindset: the teachers with years of teaching experience can perform better. They can teach; manage classes; design, develop and use teaching materials better in comparison to novice teachers. So the institutes while recruiting teachers in Nepal, especially the school level teachers expect to have teaching experience. I may not be correct but one of the reasons behind the selection of experienced teacher is time and money. After recruiting experienced teachers, they do not have to invest time and effort for novice teachers. They think that novice teachers need more time and efforts in teaching. Moreover they need training as well. This sort of misunderstanding that a novice teacher will take more time in getting familiar with the culture of the school and the students promotes the search of experienced teachers.

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Conclusion

The hypothesis that only experienced teachers can give high performance and without teaching experience teaching can never be as good as it should be, has been falsified as article has concluded that even a novice teacher who has enough content knowledge also can teach better, and make students satisfied. It means the paradigm of taking teaching experience as everything has no any logic behind rather it is a copy cat mentality where one does wrong and other follows same. The only reason behind the job rejection should not be teaching experience. Similarly, it further concluded that the content knowledge and teaching experience both seem equally essential for teacher's professional development. So the competency of the subject and teaching experience both should have equal space in teacher selection. **References**

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